

DRAFT DATA-SHARING MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Authors of this deliverable: Rita Banzi (IRFMN), Sergio Contrino (ECRIN), Giulia Irene Guilardi (IRFMN), Mihaela Matei (ECRIN), Maria Alexandra Rujano (ECRIN), Birgit Schaffhauser (MIP), eCREAM Consortium.

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enabling **C**linical **R**esearch in **E**mergency and **A**cute care **M**edicine through automated data extraction

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Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
App	Application
ASTIR	ASTIR SRL
CHUV	Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CSV	Comma-Separated Values file
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EBRAINS	digital research infrastructure for brain science and brain-inspired technology
eCREAM	Enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction
ED	Emergency Departments
ED-EHR	Electronic Health Record for the ED
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHR	Electronic Health Records
EL	DIOIKHSH YGEIONOMIKHS PERIFEREIAS KRHTHS
ELE	European Language Equality
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
FBK	Fondazione Bruno Kessler
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resource
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HBP	Human Brain Project
HL7	Health Level 7
HL7 CDA2	HL7 Clinical Document Architecture, Release 2
IHE	Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise
IRFMN	Istituto Di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri
IT	Information technology
M55	Month 55
MIP	Medical Information Platform
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OpenEHR	Open Electronic Health Records
OROBIX	OROBIX LIFE SRL
PL	Uniwersytet Jagiellonski
RESTful	Representational State Transfer
RI	Research Infrastructure
SI	Univerzitetni klinicni center Maribor
SK	Univerzita Pavla Jozefa Safarika V Kosiciach
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
VLO	Virtual Language Observatory
VM	Virtual Machine
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document is a first version of the consortium's data sharing and management plan (DMP), covering ethical and legal issues. The DMP is intended to evolve over the course of the project and a final updated version will be provided as deliverable 5.3 at M55.

It first describes the data that will be collected and processed as part of the project and the related data flows. It then illustrates the planned strategy for making the services and databases created in the project adhere as much as possible to the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al, 2016), with particular regards to the project's two use cases.

A final part describes the steps taken to insure the correctness of the ethical and legal approach of the project.

1- Aim and scope

The main objective of the eCREAM project is to enable clinical research and quality of care assessment using data extracted directly from electronic health records (EHR) in emergency departments (ED). To achieve this objective we aim to develop new technical solutions to extract reliable clinical information from structured and unstructured data contained in electronic patient files and to insure that this information is available to different stakeholders (clinicians, researchers, health policymakers and citizens) following where possible the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al, 2016) while respecting the European and national legislations. We want to apply this general concept to two relevant use cases: i) the assessment of ED propensity to hospitalise a patient, and ii) the development of a dashboard to be used by citizens and policymakers to improve the quality of care in ED.

This plan illustrates our strategy for insuring a good level of FAIRness of the services and databases created to address the two use cases, and in this way to increase their usability by a variety of users outside the consortium (e.g. patients' advocacy groups, clinicians, policymakers, and researchers). The goal is to maximise the exploitation of the collected data for secondary research and monitoring activities. The strategy wants to ensure compliance with ethical, legal and societal issues (ELSI) requirements, especially with the GDPR and national implementations of data protection regulations. We are basing our approach on the FAIRification process defined by the GO FAIR initiative (<https://www.go-fair.org>) as well as recommendations for FAIRification workflows specific to healthcare. We plan to embed the project's outputs into the current European data sharing landscape of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

This document describes the data that will be collected and processed, the current status of the FAIRification strategy and the current knowledge about the national legal framework for data management in the participating countries.

2- Data summary

eCREAM will create three different databases of clinical data gathered from EDs located in six European countries: Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, UK. The collected data will then be anonymised, processed and made available to the different stakeholders. Please refer also to Appendix 2 for more details on the data flows and the legal bases of the process.

2.1 Natural Language Processing (NLP) (WP1)

For each language considered (English, Greek, Italian, Polish, Slovakian, Slovenian), a huge number (hundreds of millions) of words is needed to train the artificial intelligence algorithm. For this reason, ways to collect free text notes both in a retrospective (for algorithm training) and prospective (see case studies) way from collaborating Emergency Departments (EDs) need to be explored.

In this context, eCREAM will re-use these textual (unstructured) notes written by emergency physicians and nurses, covering a large variety of clinical information (i.e., diagnoses, syndromes, signs, and symptoms). No other structured clinical information will be collected.

The data will be collected by the collaborating EDs (Appendix 1), which will pre-process (anonymise) the data, and deposit them in the NLP-eCREAM databases hosted by the Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK, Italy), in charge of developing the algorithm. The collected data will then be used to train the artificial intelligence algorithm responsible for extracting structured information from textual notes. This structured information will then be utilised in our use cases (specifically use case 1, see below).

Outside the project, the NLP-eCREAM database could become a useful resource for the research community, in particular for NLP training in a clinical setting. Whether and how the data will be accessible beyond eCREAM is being explored.

The training of the Natural Language Process will benefit from as much data collected as possible. At the moment for the first phase of the study we foresee processing around 1.5 billion documents of general medical domain in the 6 languages of the project (English, Greek, Italian, Slovak, Slovenian, Polish).

2.2 Use Case 1 (WP4): Measuring the propensity of EDs to hospitalise patients

Use case 1 aims to build an adjusted indicator for measuring the propensity of EDs to hospitalise patients. Therefore, it is necessary to collect a specific set of clinical and organisational information (predictors) to feed a mathematical prediction model. Case study 1 will focus on patients presenting loss of consciousness or dyspnoea at ED arrival. Patients included in Case study 1 will be treated according to the ED routine clinical practice, and there will not be any additional data collection. The study is purely observational.

The detailed definition of the predictors (data) that should be collected is ongoing. In general, we will need the following:

- Characteristics of the patients: age, sex, race/ethnicity, mode of arrival to the ED and arrival day/time
- Signs, symptoms, attributed emergency level
- Results of diagnostic procedures.

Collaborating EDs will thus provide EHRs of attending patients in the 2 categories considered by the study, i.e. patients presenting loss of consciousness or dyspnoea at ED arrival. The data collected will be used to feed a mathematical prediction model which will estimate the propensity of each ED to hospitalise patients.

The data will be centralised in the clinical-eCREAM database hosted by the Mario Negri Institute (IRFMN) and will be made accessible beyond eCREAM through the Medical Information Platform (MIP), an online collaborative tool managed by Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois (CHUV) to foster further research in emergency medicine.

2.3 Use case 2 (WP4): Development of a multipurpose dashboard

The aim of this use case is to develop a multipurpose dashboard to inform end-users about predefined characteristics of the EDs in real time. The dashboard will be set up for two end-user categories: citizens and health policymakers. eCREAM will develop an App to be used by citizens to check the crowding level at each

ED, the number of patients waiting by emergency code, and the average waiting time for the visit by emergency code. Health policymakers will have access to data to monitor specific organisational (e.g., boarding time) and epidemiological (e.g., the emergence of infectious disease) phenomena. As with Use case 1, patients will be treated according to the ED routine clinical practice and there will not be any additional data collection. The study is purely observational.

To create a real-time dashboard, the following information will be extracted every 5 minutes from each ED:

- Number of patients waiting and their waiting time stratified by patient sex, age, emergency code, and major acute symptom at triage.
- Number of patients receiving treatment and average duration of treatment stratified by sex, age, emergency code and major acute symptom at triage.
- The time of arrival of the ambulances and the time to release them for the next emergency.

The temporal data collected in this way will be fed into and provide inputs to a dashboard application.

The data will be collected and pre-processed (aggregated and anonymised) by the participating hospitals, deposited in the 'organisational-eCREAM databases' and used by the dashboard application. An initial estimation of the size of the data collected for this part of the project is 100 GB.

Two different dashboards will be developed, one that will benefit the general public (level of affluence in each ED, number of patients waiting per emergency code, and the average waiting time for the visit per emergency code) and the control panel for health care providers and policy makers that will allow the monitoring of specific organisational (e.g. boarding time) and epidemiological (e.g. the emergence of infectious disease) phenomena. The application and control panel will be multilingual. The application will be developed for use on Android and iOS. The control panel will provide differentiated access according to user profile and will allow the download of data and reports. Both modules will be validated by the key users involved in drafting the protocol.

3- FAIR data

3.1 Findability

Data for the three tasks will be stored in different databases. To be Findable, data will be described by adequate metadata readable by both humans and computers and identified by globally unique and persistent identifiers which is essential for the automatic discovery of datasets and services. eCREAM will collect and make available information about the generation, location, format, provenance, handling and governance of data, linked to data by data identifiers.

Metadata will comply with domain-relevant community standards and be registered/indexed in searchable resources. The metadata will cover: i) Metadata of existing health data catalogues and collections used in the project; ii) Glossary on health data and health data management and terms, to unify the terminology among the project and related centres; iii) Catalogue of characteristics of health data curation and governance on local data hubs.

3.2 Accessibility

3.2.1 Repository:

eCREAM will build its own repositories and will register them in FAIRsharing.org, a catalogue of databases (<https://fairsharing.org/databases/>), allowing discovery and search for potential users. Services developed within eCREAM, such as the web-based dashboard, will be integrated into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Portal Catalogue and Marketplace (<https://marketplace.eoscportal.eu/>).

eCREAM will also create a significant linguistic dataset resource from the annotated and non annotated ED texts used to train the eCREAM NLP models. This dataset has great potential for further medical NLP innovation and we plan to share it through the main European platforms for language resources, including the European Language Grid repository (<https://live.europeanlanguage-grid.eu>), the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory (CLARIN VLO) (<https://vlo.clarin.eu/?2>), and the European Language Equality (ELE) initiative (<https://european-language-equality.eu>).

3.2.2 Data:

eCREAM will set up a multilevel operational access model to maximise openness to various end-users and to satisfy the need to comply with data protection regulations in force in Europe. Access to users will be through the MIP, a Global Open-Source Platform allowing hospitals and research centres worldwide to share medical data. Data privacy and safety will be handled according to the following principles:

- Data harmonisation/preparation will be performed by the data managers at each site outside the MIP and only the final anonymised dataset will be uploaded into the various MIP instances, with no pseudo-identifier available.
- The MIP user interface does not allow access, explore, manipulate, copy or download the CSV file containing the data: manipulation of data files can only be performed by authorised personnel who get access to the server where the files are being stored. The MIP user interface only allows selecting datasets, variables of interest, ranges of values, and applying statistical queries (descriptive, analytical) on this selection.
- The queries can only provide aggregated findings calculated on at least 10 subjects, thus hampering any possibility to perform indirect re-identification of individual subjects by reconstructing their profile through a specific query.
- According to the anonymised nature of the MIP datasets, upgrades of the latter require replacing the entire current dataset with the upgraded one using the same procedure as that used to enter the first dataset in the MIP. This upgrade can be used to manage consent withdrawal and provision of new data/cases.
- All end-users of the MIP eCREAM federation will need to be accredited by the eCREAM steering committee to be authorised to query the federated datasets. Furthermore, authorizations are dataset specific.
- The multi-purpose dashboard application will also provide programmatic access via Application Programming Interface (API) end points.

3.2.3 Metadata:

Metadata will be open by default to any user in two ways. Firstly, all end-users registered to the public MIP will be able to see, through its front-end, the data model that describes all the eCREAM database variables. In addition, the knowledge graph developed by the Human Brain Project (HBP) and publicly available at EBRAINS (<https://ebrains.eu/>), will expose the same information as well as all other relevant metadata, as the number of patients available in the eCREAM database. Other strategies for making metadata available to the scientific community will be explored, taking advantage of synergies between eCREAM and the current European data sharing landscape of the EHDS and the EOSC.

Data will be centrally stored for 20 years from the closing date of the study. At that time all data collected for this study will be definitively deleted, unless considered particularly relevant for scientific purposes: in such an eventuality a specific authorization to continue their exploitation will be issued to the competent local/national ethical boards/bodies.

3.3 Interoperability

Integration of databases and services with the MIP developed in the HBP (Task 5.3) will ensure accessibility to various end-users and compliance with the European and national data protection regulations. Furthermore, the integration of existing EHR systems (WP2) and creation of a de-novo EHR to be used by EDs (WP3) will ensure the Interoperability of the different eCREAM data sources. We plan to make this new specialised EHR public.

eCREAM will define and implement interoperability modules (as a software) that will ensure the interface of the new electronic health record for the ED (ED-EHR) with the other components of the eCREAM architecture and with the information systems in use in the EDs in which the ED-EHR will be deployed. The modules will expose interoperability RESTful (Representational State Transfer) or SOAP (Simple Object Access Protocol) APIs to implement the communications with the other systems. To ensure semantic interoperability, the modules will be based on the adoption of international communication standards for the exchange of clinical/administrative documents and resources (e.g. HL7 CDA2, FHIR, IHE, OpenEHR archetypes), which could be defined after the context analysis in the target EDs. The specific choice will depend on a context analysis, which will precede the design of ED-EHR.

3.4 Reusability

Reusability will be supported via different open eCREAM outputs. eCREAM databases will be made available for re-use, according to transparent, accountable access mechanisms, compliant to ethical and legal standards at the EU level, within the framework of Open Science.

The eCREAM database, created to address the two use cases, will be available to the community for re-use according to three different approaches using various MIP:

- Public-MIP: The public MIP is a MIP instance installed on the publicly available EBRAINS infrastructure. The latter, developed by HBP, has recently been labelled European Research Infrastructure and offers a sustainable, state-of-the-art IT environment for storing and sharing data, using the public MIP and other tools. Any person wishing to access the public MIP needs to register to get EBRAINS accredited (personal or institutional accreditation) and can then analyse online any data placed in that public MIP using the MIP analytical tools. The public MIP will include a subset of the eCREAM database made publicly available to a broader community, including citizens. For instance, sex, age, the priority code assigned at the triage, main signs and symptoms prompting the ED visit, and the final disposition decision on hospitalisation will be uploaded to the Public-MIP. The eCREAM steering committee will define the complete list of variables to make available on the Public- MIP.

- eCREAM-MIP: The eCREAM-MIP will be installed as a secure, dedicated Virtual Machine (VM) integrated into the EBRAINS RI. It will contain the eCREAM database (central database) and access to it will be restricted to a defined set of end-users accredited by the eCREAM steering committee. The overall MIP security system (EBRAINS Identity and Access management: EBRAINS accreditation and EBRAINS MIP Keycloak authentication, delineating, implementing and controlling the access rights of each accredited end-user of the federation) provides programmatic access for each user. All analyses and outputs are systematically recorded and associated with the user's credentials, providing full traceability of data access and analyses. The level of exposure is dependent on the specific user access rights and relevant EBRAINS and MIP policies. To best manage the growing MIP network, an extended version of the MIP Secure VPN will be implemented to provide common, over-the-top and firewall-friendly network topologies for data transport, remote access, and connectivity and infrastructure interoperability across all data modules.

- Federated-MIP: The federated-MIP will permit installation of other MIP instances at Participant organisations wishing to federate their data with the eCREAM-MIP. Alternative set-ups entail the provision of remote node instances at partner organisations, which become part of a domain-specific federation,

connecting the remote nodes to the central MIP operating on the EBRAINS RI; or the MIP federated nodes are pre-configured as “private” and secured virtual machines (planned for the eCREAM-MIP), dedicated to specific partners and preinstalled on the EBRAINS RI. Like in the remote node federation, dedicated VMs connect to the central MIP on EBRAINS that controls the federation. A mixed setup is possible, tailoring the solution to end-user requirements. Organising such federation involves several essential steps, including installation of the MIP at each site willing to participate, harmonising these other datasets according to the eCREAM data model, connecting the different MIP to a central MIP operating in EBRAINS, and delineating, implementing and controlling the access rights of each accredited end-user of the federation. The overall MIP security system enables to define which data can be made available to each user (see above). Moreover, all analyses and outputs are systematically recorded and associated with the user’s credentials, thus providing full control over data analyses. We plan to document and publish our processes and methods to make them available to the research community.

4- Allocation of resources

The costs for the software, computation and storage of data for the project are summarised in the table 1 below, which includes also the costs of dissemination and publication. They are compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions and will be covered by the grant. Most of the human resources of the project are also devoted to the treatment of data.

The overall management of data for the project rests with the project leader (IRFMN), while package leaders are responsible for their specific part of the project (FBK, Astir).

Table 1. Allocation of resources related to data.

Partner	Data related expenses	WP/Task	Costs in €
IRFMN	High-tech company “3M”, which is a third party of IFRMN (to produce semi-automatic annotation of at least 20000 text notes coming from different EHRs	WP1/T1.2	60.000
	IT providers to modify the existing EHR	WP2/T2.6	80.000
	Cluster activities	WP8/T8.6	15.000
	Equipment/storage		36.000
	Publication costs	WP8/T8.2	23.000
Orobix	Costs related to go-to-market consultancy services for the AI cloud platform. Professional support to write a Business Plan for the clinical stratification tool, in particular by leveraging expertise on EHR market actors, including EHR vendors, integrators and potential customers	WP8/T8.5	5.000
	Cloud Computing Costs for the development of AI models: stratification and nowcasting modules	WP4/T4.9	10.000
	UI mockup realisation and frontend development for the stratification module	WP4/T4.4	10.000
	Publication costs	WP8/T8.2	3.000
FKB	Cluster activities	WP8/T8.6	17.500
	2 iTesla V100 GPU PCI-E 64GB RAM based on Microsoft Azure platform	WP1/T1.3	33.300
	Publication costs	WP8/T8.2	15.000
EL	IT providers to modify the existing EHR	WP2/T2.6	32.000
	Publication costs	WP8/T8.2	15.000

Astir	Cloud Services: 4 Virtual Machine t4g.xlarge Amazon EC2 based in EU (Frankfurt) dedicated to the Astir sw components x 3 years	WP2 WP6	12.000
	Cloud Services: DB - MySQL db.m5.4xlarge 100GB Amazon RDS for MySQL based in EU (Frankfurt) x 3 years	WP2 WP6	21.000
	Cloud Services: 6 VPN Machine Amazon EC2 based in EU (Frankfurt) x 3 years	WP2 WP6	19.000
	Cloud Services: 4 Virtual Machine t4g.xlarge Amazon EC2 based in EU (Frankfurt) dedicated to the partner sw components x 3 years	WP2 WP6	12.000
	Cloud Services: Virtual Private Network support x 6 VPN x 3 years	WP2 WP6	26.000
	Cluster activities	WP8/T8.6	17.500
SI	IT providers to modify the existing EHR	WP2/T2.2, 2.6	30.000
	Software	WP2	5.000
SK	IT providers to modify the existing EHR	WP2/T2.2, 2.6	30.000
	Publication costs	WP8/T8.2	5.000
PL	IT providers to modify the existing EHR	WP2/T2.6	30.000
	Publication costs	WP8/T8.2	2.500
	Software	WP2	4.000
	15% of the depreciation costs of server	WP2-WP5	3.000

5- Data Quality and Data security

5.1 Data quality

The ED-EHR will be equipped with a virtual assistant which performs real time data quality validations. The virtual assistant will provide support in validating data quality, by detecting data inconsistencies (e.g. incorrect date format), implausibility (e.g. parameter values out of possible ranges), logical incongruences (e.g. ED discharge date preceding the admission date), possible clinical incongruences (e.g. a patient with an infectious disease without reported fever), alarming situations (e.g. prescription of a drug in the case of known allergies).

Other Data Quality Control:

- Mandatory set of data needed to enter a patient.
- Patients can be tagged for a complete review or if they need to be completed.
- On-demand statistics to track inconsistencies or incompleteness.
- Online help pages (patient form, data queries).

5.2 Data security

eCREAM's tools will be developed considering the following technical aspects of to ensure data security (e.g. access) and integrity (e.g. backups):

Database security and capacities:

- Full https encryption with a certificate from an official authority.

- All personal data able to identify the patient will be stored only locally, in encrypted form. The central database will not contain any such information.
- Business level security model based on roles and centres.
- Daily backup.
- Data is hosted on dedicated servers.
- History tracked for user login/logout.
- History tracked for patient creation/update/deletion.
- Journal of modifications by user/centre/patient/date.

6- Ethical and legal aspects

The eCREAM consortium includes 11 partners from 8 European countries (France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland, UK). To ensure compliance with ethical and legal requirements, it is essential to assess the ethical, legal and social issues (ELSI) related to the project's data processing activities in each participant country.

6.1 Ethical aspects

Given the objectives of this project, the ethical issues should focus on the security of the collection of health data. All tools developed within eCREAM will comply with international, European and national laws relating to clinical research involving human subjects. All Consortium Partners undertake to follow all ethical, legal and regulatory standards of Good Clinical Practice. In particular, they will operate in accordance with:

- Declaration of Helsinki (2013)
- EU Directive 2005/28/EC of 8 April 2005 on good clinical practice
- General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679)
- Universal Declaration on the human genome and human rights adopted by UNESCO
- Oviedo Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine (1997/04/04)
- EU Regulation 745/2017 on medical devices

Before proceeding with the clinical studies, the study protocols will be submitted to the ethics committee of each hospital involved in the project for approval, opinion or notification, in accordance with national legislation.

6.1.1 Humans and Personal data

No incentives for patient participation will be provided, but every effort will be made to ensure that all eligible patients are recruited, also considering that, due to the inherent observational nature of the project, no risk is associated with patient participation.

The project foresees the involvement of vulnerable populations, as data automatically extracted from the EHR of all adult patients presenting to the ED will be processed. Special measures will be put in place to ensure adequate protection of the rights and wellbeing of vulnerable subjects. A dedicated, simplified but still complete information leaflet will be prepared and given to these patients and their caregivers.

The partners involved in WP4 are all experienced in guiding and assessing medical research protocols in the light of applicable global and EU regulations. Moreover, health data transfer agreements between IRFMN

and CHUV, and between IRFMN and other hospitals in the UK are already in place, to prove the viability to share and transfer data with the non-EU countries involved in eCREAM (UK and Switzerland).

6.1.2 Artificial intelligence

A virtual assistant will be integrated into the eCREAM ED-EHR. It will interact in real time with the user (clinicians) to reduce missing data, improve the comparability of coding between different centres, increase the internal consistency of the clinical documentation and disambiguate the reconstruction of the decision-making strategy. This assistant will not make decisions for clinicians and will not limit their ability to make diagnoses or prescriptions. Artificial intelligence will also be used to develop an AI-based nowcasting model to predict in the short term the number of patients arriving at the emergency room by priority code. This model will be implemented both in the application to allow citizens to choose the most appropriate ED to go to, and in the web-based control panel to inform different types of health organisations and policy makers of the real-time ED situation and its possible short-term evolution. In order to avoid making biased predictions, the model will be validated before being implemented in the system.

6.2 Legal aspects

To determine the legal framework applicable to the data processing activities (data collection, data processing and data flows) involved in the project tasks, four steps have been put in place:

6.2.1 Working group

The consortium has set up a dedicated working group with experts (legal experts and DPOs) representing all sites involved in the project. Their main task is to help the beneficiaries of the project to identify the legal and regulatory constraints required under the national legal framework in the countries of the participating ED (Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Slovakia, Greece and UK). Their advice will be collected by an operational and legal questionnaire. Specific meetings with the working group will be held in March 2023 and whenever necessary to address legal issues.

6.2.2 Data flows and legal bases for data collection and processing document

A document drafted on 23 February 2023 (Appendix 2) was created with the aim of a) describing the data that will be collected and processed within the scope of eCREAM and the corresponding data flows, b) to propose solutions to collect and process these data in a safe and legal way, in accordance with European and national legal frameworks, c) to support each national partner involved in data collection in the discussion with the competent authorities (local, regional, national if applicable) and to identify the most appropriate approach for data collection and processing and d) to set the legal framework to be included in the eCREAM study protocol(s).

6.2.3 Operational and legal questionnaire

In order to get some clarity on the legal and regulatory requirements which are applicable in relation to the project activities, we have developed a specific questionnaire (provided as appendix 3) which addresses the operational and legal questions in relation to the data processing activities.

The purpose of this questionnaire is to get a clear overview of data processing activities throughout the project in order to determine the legal requirements and legal risks. It addresses operational and legal issues e.g. categories of personal data, data flows, data transfer, legal and regulatory constraints: legal basis, regulatory submission, etc. It is divided into 3-4 sections according to the type of activities that involve the processing of personal data (MIP, NLP, Use case 1, Use case 2, etc).

The operational questions have been already addressed by the concerned beneficiaries and their answers are being provided directly in appendix 3.

The questionnaire was sent to the legal representatives/DPOs of the clinical sites (data providers) on February 10, 2023 to collect information regarding the legal constraints and the legal risks associated with data transfer/sharing. The goal is to collect information on the applicable legal and regulatory framework in every country as well as the conditions under which the participating clinical sites can provide patient-related data in the context of the eCREAM project. Answers are due by March 1, 2023.

6.2.4 Identification of contracting parties and contractual relationships

A list of relevant contracting parties (Data Providers and Data Recipients) will be created, and the contract flow (data transfer and data sharing activities) will be determined. Then, based on the information gathered through the questionnaire, a discussion can be initiated between the relevant contracting parties and any additional legal risks (related to procurement and regulatory constraints) can be identified.

Reference

Wilkinson MD, et al: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data*. 2016 Mar 15;3:160018. doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.

Erratum in: *Sci Data*. 2019 Mar 19;6(1):6. PMID: 26978244; PMCID: PMC4792175.

Appendix 1. LIST OF PARTICIPATING EMERGENCY DEPARTMENTS

Clinical site/Hospital	Country	Province
Papa Giovanni XXIII	Italy	Bergamo
ASST Sacco	Italy	Milan
Policlinico Ospedale Maggiore	Italy	Milan
ASST Grande H Metropolitano Niguarda	Italy	Milan
Ospedale di Circolo e Fondazione Macchi	Italy	Varese
AO SS. Antonio e Biagio e C. Arrigo	Italy	Alessandria
San Martino	Italy	Genova
San Luigi Gonzaga	Italy	Otbassano
Ospedale degli Infermi	Italy	Rivoli
Ospedale San Giovanni Bosco	Italy	Torino
Ospedale Sant'Andrea	Italy	Torino
ASUFC	Italy	Udine
Ospedale Maggiore Carlo Alberto Pizzardi	Italy	Bologna
Ospedale Santa Maria Annunziata	Italy	Florence
Azienda ospedaliera di Perugia	Italy	Perugia
Ospedale Sant'Eugenio	Italy	Rome
Santa Maria delle Grazie	Italy	Pozzuoli
Presidio Ospedaliero Gaspare Rodolico	Italy	Catania
University General Hospital of Heraklion	Greece	Heraklion
General Hospital of Chania	Greece	Chania
General Hospital of Rethymnon	Greece	Rethymnon
General Hospital "Venizeleio-Pananeio"	Greece	Heraklion
General Hospital of Agios Nikolaos	Greece	Lasithi
Uniwersytet Jagiellonski	Poland	Kraków
Hospital Emergency Ward, Military Hospital	Poland	Kraków
Stefan Zeromsky Specialist Hospital	Poland	Kraków
University Hospital Krakow	Poland	Kraków
Univerzita Pavla Jozefa Safarika v Kosiciach	Slovakia	Košice
East Slovakian Cardiovascular Institute	Slovakia	Nové Mesto
L. Pasteur University Hospital	Slovakia	Košice
AGEL Hospital	Slovakia	Ružinov
Univerzitetni klinicni center Maribor	Slovenia	Maribor
General Hospital Izola	Slovenia	Izola
General Hospital Jesenice	Slovenia	Jesenice
Ashford and St Peter's Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust	UK	Surrey
Royal Surrey County Hospital	UK	Guildford
Frimley Park Hospital	UK	Camberley

Appendix 2. Data flows and legal bases for data collection and processing

V7. 23 February 2023

IRFMN (Rita Banzi, Guido Bertolini, Giulia Ghilardi)

ECRIN (Mihaela Matei)

Preamble

The eCREAM project - **enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine** - is a 5-year Horizon Europe project led by the Mario Negri Institute for Pharmacological Research (IRFMN, Italy). The eCREAM consortium includes 11 partners from 8 European countries (France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland, UK).

The central aim of the project is to enable clinical and quality of care assessment research using data extracted directly **from electronic health records (EHR) of emergency departments (ED)**.

To reach this goal eCREAM has three main objectives:

- to develop new technical solutions to extract reliable clinical information from structured and unstructured data contained in different electronic patient files;
- to pilot the exploitation of the established databases in two relevant use cases: i) assessment of ED propensity to hospitalise a patient, and ii) development of a dashboard to be used by citizens and policymakers to improve the quality of care in ED
- to FAIRify (i.e., making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable) the established databases for clinicians, researchers, health policymakers and citizens while respecting the European and national legislations.

To achieve the project objectives, eCREAM will create **three different databases** of clinical data gathered from EDs located in six European countries: Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, UK.

Purpose of this document

- To describe the data that will be collected and processed within the perimeter of the eCREAM project and the corresponding data flows
- To propose solutions to collect and process these data safely and lawfully, according to the EU and national legal frameworks.
- To support each national partner of eCREAM involved in data collection in the discussion with the competent authorities (local, regional, national if applicable) and identify the most adequate approach to data collection and processing.
- To set the legal framework to be included in the eCREAM study protocol(s).

1- Natural Language Processing

Most information related to ED patients is contained in textual (i.e., unstructured) notes compiled by emergency physicians and nurses. Natural language processing (NLP) and text analytics involve using machine learning algorithms and artificial intelligence to understand the meaning of text documents. The eCREAM project will use NLP tool tailored to the typical notes made by emergency physicians and nurses to maximize the retrieval of high-quality data from routine practice. The development of an NLP system for the emergency medicine clinical domain requires a combination of unsupervised and supervised methods, based on a huge number (hundreds of millions) of words to train the artificial intelligence algorithm.

Project’s needs: The information source needed for developing the NLP system includes clinical notes derived from the collaborating EDs of the eCREAM project. For each language considered by the project (English, Greek, Italian, Polish, Slovakian, Slovenian), we should explore ways to collect clinical notes both in a retrospective and prospective way from the electronic health records. Figure 1 reports an example of a typical note in an ED Clinical Diary and how the data will be structured and extracted for the NLP training. No other structured clinical information will be collected with textual notes.

ED CLINICAL DIARY (the text is coloured according to the different dimensions to explore)													
<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <th style="text-align: center;">Present complaint</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Male, 79y. Presents after a loss of consciousness during the night in standing position post-micturition. Recalls a sudden onset of light-headedness just before loosing consciousness. Reports a mild head injury in the fall. Upon awakening, patient called 999 on his own. No PTA. Does not report recent similar episodes.</td> </tr> <tr> <th style="text-align: center;">Social history</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Pt lives alone, caregiver a few hours a day.</td> </tr> <tr> <th style="text-align: center;">Past medical history</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Hypertension, benign prostatic hyperplasia, mild chronic kidney disease, CHD (PTCA).</td> </tr> <tr> <th style="text-align: center;">Drug history</th> </tr> <tr> <td>tamsulosin, enalapril, ASA 100 mg, statin, bisoprolol, lormetazepam. NKDA</td> </tr> </table>	Present complaint	Male, 79y. Presents after a loss of consciousness during the night in standing position post-micturition. Recalls a sudden onset of light-headedness just before loosing consciousness. Reports a mild head injury in the fall. Upon awakening, patient called 999 on his own. No PTA. Does not report recent similar episodes.	Social history	Pt lives alone, caregiver a few hours a day.	Past medical history	Hypertension, benign prostatic hyperplasia, mild chronic kidney disease, CHD (PTCA).	Drug history	tamsulosin, enalapril, ASA 100 mg, statin, bisoprolol, lormetazepam. NKDA	<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <th style="text-align: center;">On examination</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Airway - patent Breathing - Sat 98%, RR 16, chest clear, no shortness of breath Circulation – BP 130/70, HR 82, WWP. Normal S1 and S2 heart sounds. No oedema. Disability – GCS 15, pupil, equal, round, reactive to light and accommodation, cranial nerve 2-12 intact, 5/5 strength in all extremities bilaterally Expose – T 35.8. Abdomen soft non tender. No other sign of trauma, no c-spine pain, no pelvic pain. EKG: sinus rhythm, 80 bpm, old inferior q wave, non specific ST-T changes. Cardiac POCUS: EF approximately 30%.</td> </tr> <tr> <th style="text-align: center;">Conclusion</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Vasovagal syncope</td> </tr> </table>	On examination	Airway - patent Breathing - Sat 98%, RR 16, chest clear, no shortness of breath Circulation – BP 130/70, HR 82, WWP. Normal S1 and S2 heart sounds. No oedema. Disability – GCS 15, pupil, equal, round, reactive to light and accommodation, cranial nerve 2-12 intact, 5/5 strength in all extremities bilaterally Expose – T 35.8. Abdomen soft non tender. No other sign of trauma, no c-spine pain, no pelvic pain. EKG: sinus rhythm, 80 bpm, old inferior q wave, non specific ST-T changes. Cardiac POCUS: EF approximately 30%.	Conclusion	Vasovagal syncope
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Conclusion													
Vasovagal syncope													

<u>DIMENSION TO EXPLORE</u>	<u>VARIABLES TO RETRIEVE</u>	<u>VALUES TO BE EXTRACTED BY NLP</u>
Patient frailty	Sex and Age	Male, 79 years
	Functional status	Lives alone, caregiver a few hours a day
	Comorbidity	Hypertension, Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia, Chronic Kidney Disease, Coronary Artery Disease (PTCA)
	Drug history	tamsulosin, enalapril, ASA, statin, bisoprolol, lormetazepam, NKDA
Syncope’s features	Prodromal symptoms	Light-headedness
	Trigger	Post-micturition
	Conditions upon awakening	Aware (deduced), no PTA
	Palpitations	No (deduced)
Consequences	Brain injury	Mild, without bleedings
	Fractures	No
Exams	EKG	Sinus rhythm, 80 bpm, old inferior q wave, non-specific ST-T changes
	Lab	No
	Echocardiography	EF approximately 30%
	Monitor	Yes

PTA: Post-traumatic amnesia CHD: Coronary Artery Disease PTCA: Percutaneous transluminal coronary angioplasty ASA: Acetylsalicylic acid NKDA: No Known Drug Allergies	GCS: Glasgow Coma Scale WWP: Warm Well Perfused EKG: Electrocardiogram POCUS: Point-of-care ultrasound
---	---

Figure 1

Type of data: Textual (unstructured) notes written by emergency physicians and nurses, covering a large variety of clinical information (i.e., diagnoses, syndromes, signs, and symptoms).

Data flow (Figure 2): The participating hospitals will retrospectively and prospectively collect the data, pre-process them to remove possible identifiers (see below), and centralize them to the NLP-eCREAM databases

hosted by Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK, Italy). To be explored whether and how these data will be made accessible beyond eCREAM (FBK).

Figure 2

Data classification: Normally, textual notes do not include personal data. However, there might be a few exceptions, including the inclusion of personal data of other subjects incidentally mentioned (e.g., caregiver names or phone numbers).

Pre-processing of data: Strategies to automatically remove personal data (name and surname, address, telephone number, calendar dates) from clinical notes exist and will be applied before the transfer from the hospital (data owner/controller) to FBK (data processor). Technical specifications of the anonymisation system and risk assessment will be duly included in the study protocol that will be submitted to the ethical committees and other authorities according to national provisions. Data will be stored in the NLP-eCREAM databases without any reference to the ED where they have been collected.

Pre-processing may not be needed in those countries where collection and processing of data for health research can be normally allowed on the basis GDPR Article 6 (e) or (f) (performance of a task carried out in the **public interest** or in the exercise of official authority vested the controller or for the purposes of the **legitimate interests**)

Legal basis for collecting and processing data: The approach described above makes the data fully anonymized; consequently, their processing falls outside the GDPR. Accordingly, the request for explicit consent to collect and re-use these data should not be applicable.

The NLP protocol will be submitted for approval/notification to competent Ethical Committees and other decision bodies according to national laws.

2- Measuring the propensity of EDs to hospitalize patients

ED performance is characterised by a series of decision-making steps, ranging from rapidly defining the priority with which patients will undergo a medical examination (triage), to establishing whether they need hospitalisation. The IT-solutions developed by eCREAM will be tested in this latter scenario, one of the most critical in emergency medicine, due to the possible adverse consequences in both management (related to inappropriate hospitalisations) and clinical terms (related to inappropriate discharge). The decision to admit or discharge a patient from the ED is influenced, among other things, by patient-specific factors (e.g., medical condition), physician-specific factors (e.g., self-defined risk thresholds), hospital-specific factors (e.g., availability of medical resources), and societal-specific factors (e.g., presence of healthcare services).

eCREAM will conduct an observational study to build adjusted indicator(s) for measuring the propensity of EDs to hospitalize patients. This study is named “Case study 1” in the following section of this document, and it will focus on patients with loss of consciousness or dyspnoea at ED arrival.

These indicators will provide a single ED with a thorough representation of its propensity to hospitalise patients, compared to the average behaviour, overall, over time, and according to the patient’s probability of being hospitalised. While the indicators are not aimed at measuring the appropriateness of the decision, they will facilitate a revision of the clinical practice of the participating EDs to improve healthcare quality and outcome.

The indicators developed will provide every ED with a thorough representation of its propensity to hospitalise patients, compared to the average behaviour, overall, over time, and according to the patient’s probability of being hospitalised. Considering that the hospitalisation rate is one of the most commonly used indicators of the quality of care for Emergency Departments, this project will facilitate a revision of the clinical practice of the participating EDs to improve healthcare quality and outcomes. Case study 1 will, in other words, produce an unprecedented benchmarking model for quality-of-care assessment, allowing the monitoring of the propensity to admit patients of each ED, the comparison among different centres, and the planning of correcting measures.

Interestingly, the participation of several EDs from different countries, and the possibility of pooling their data for analysis, will allow for studying the determinants of the disposition decision in terms of patients’ clinical characteristics, organizational models, and their interaction. Knowledge of these determinants will be essential not only for improving the quality of individual departments that participate in the project but also, and even more importantly, for directing policies to improve emergency medicine at large.

Ultimately, these activities represent an institutional duty of national health systems and are conducted in the public interest to improve the quality of emergency medicine.

Project’s needs:

To feed a mathematical prediction model able to estimate the propensity of each ED to hospitalise patients, there is the need to collect a specific set of clinical and organizational information (predictors). These data will be collected at the patient level through the systems already in place at each ED. Participants included in Case study 1 will be treated according to the ED routine clinical practice, and there will not be any additional data collection. Therefore, **the study is purely observational**.

Type of data:

A specific set of clinical and organizational information (predictors) will be collected to feed the mathematical prediction model to estimate the propensity of each ED to hospitalize patients.

Clinical data will be collected at the patient level through the IT systems already in place at each ED. These data will include personal data concerning health, such as:

- demographic characteristics of the patients, primarily age, sex, race/ethnicity;
- data related to patients’ admission to the ED, such as mode of arrival, day/time, main problem accused, and the attributed priority code;
- signs, symptoms, and results of diagnostic procedures. For example, information on patients presenting with dyspnoea will be grouped in seven dimensions (respiratory failure, onset of dyspnea, causes of dyspnoea, susceptibility to treatment, overall severity, frailty index, social issues). These data represent a subset of variables clinicians consider when evaluating the necessity to hospitalize a patient.

The full list of variables to be collected on patients with loss of consciousness or dyspnoea at ED arrival is under construction and will be included in the study protocol.

Organizational data will be collected at the ED level through structured questionnaires to the ED staff/head. These data will not include personal data.

Data flow (Figure 3): The participating hospitals will prospectively collect the data that will be centralized in the clinical-eCREAM database hosted by the Mario Negri Institute (IRFMN). These data will be made accessible beyond eCREAM through the Medical Information Platform (MIP), an online collaborative tool managed by Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois (CHUV) that federates patient data located in different hospitals.

Figure 3

Data classification: Data collected for Case study 1 includes **personal data concerning health**, thus their collection and processing are subject to GDPR and national provisions on health data privacy. The GDPR

Article 9 Processing of special categories of personal data prohibits the processing of these types of data unless one of the derogations defined in Article 9 Paragraph 1 applies.

Pre-processing of data: Data will be sent to the centralized **clinical-eCREAM database** (IRFMN) in a pseudonymized format.

Legal basis for collecting and processing data:

Premises:

1. Gathering the **informed consent** of all eligible participants (or their representatives) to be included in the study would undoubtedly be the most straightforward legal basis. However, as outlined below, there is the concrete risk of introducing major obstacles in the recruitment of representative patients and discouraging the participation of EDs, given the substantial additional workload. Another option would be asking for **dissent (opt-out)**, i.e., all patients would receive adequate information about the involvement of the hospital in an observational research protocol and its scope, and those eligible participants who don't want to be part of the study would sign a form of dissent. It is unclear whether this approach leads to time savings compared to the standard collection of consent and mitigates the risk of selection bias.

The burden and organization of work in the ED prevent staff from dedicating extra time to patients. Just as an example, we have calculated that at the Papa Giovanni XXIII Hospital in Bergamo (Italy), the triage nurse sees a patient every 8.5 minutes. On average, emergency doctors and nurses dedicate 20 minutes to carry out all the required clinical and administrative procedures on each patient. Demanding additional time to illustrate a research protocol, answer questions, collect consent or dissent, securely archive the documents, and communicate the decision to the study's coordinating center is untenable. There is a concrete risk that such an additional workload would discourage ED staff from carrying out research projects, preventing emergency medicine research itself. Ultimately, this may affect acute patients' care and their rights, as any other patients, to be treated according to the best evidence derived from the very same context in which they are treated. Indeed, clinical practice in emergency medicine is grounded on data collected in other settings (such as internal medicine wards) or evidence gathered in large academic centers, which can count on research-dedicated organizations and teams. These centers represent a privileged minority in the emergency medicine scenario, and the generalizability of results obtained in these contexts is very limited.

2. In the ED, patients are called upon to consent (or dissent) in critical physical and mental situations, which can lead to substantial selection bias. More severe patients will be prone to give consent, not to antagonize doctors, while less severe ones often feel their problems are underestimated and tend to refuse consent for personal reasons. Significant differences between participants and non-participants may threaten the validity of results from observational studies that require consent for the use of data from medical records. As mentioned, this may disadvantage patients in acute conditions, who cannot rely on high-level evidence.

For the reasons outlined above, the legal bases set by **GDPR Article 6 (e) or (f)** (performance of a task carried out in the **public interest** or in the exercise of official authority vested the controller or for the purposes of the **legitimate interests**) would be the most adequate considering the scientific objectives and feasibility of the project. These scenarios will encompass two possible situations:

- **Consent waiver** for organizational issues (legal basis: public interest). Due to the constraints of collecting consent from each eligible participant entering an ED, the hospital establishes as its own institutional policy its adherence to the eCREAM research projects approved by the competent Ethics

Committee and other bodies if needed. The study research protocols and their scopes will be adequately disseminated to patients and citizens.

- **Institutional duty** to improve the quality of care of the hospital (legal basis: legitimate interests). Case study 1 will produce a benchmarking model for quality-of-care assessment, allowing the monitoring of the propensity to admit patients of each ED, the comparison among different centers, and the planning of correcting measures. These activities represent hospitals' institutional duty. There is no need to ask for patients' consent to pursue an institutional duty. In this scenario, IRFMN is nominated by the hospital as an external data processor to perform the data processing needed to fulfill this service.

Irrespective of the choice of legal bases, the Case study 1 protocol will be submitted for approval to competent Ethical Committees and other decision bodies according to national laws.

3- Development of a multipurpose dashboard for citizens and policymakers

Project's needs: The aim of this use case is to develop a multipurpose dashboard to inform end-users about predefined characteristics of the EDs in real-time. We will set up the dashboard for two end-user categories: citizens and health policymakers. eCREAM will develop an App to be used by **citizens** to check the crowding level at each ED, the number of patients waiting by emergency code, and the average waiting time for the visit by emergency code. **Health policymakers** will have access to data to monitor specific organizational (e.g., boarding time) and epidemiological (e.g., the emergence of infectious disease) phenomena. As with Case study 1, patients will be treated according to the ED routine clinical practice, and there will not be any additional data collection. **The study is purely observational.**

Type of data: To create a real-time dashboard, we will extract, every 5 minutes, from each ED the following:

- number of patients awaiting a visit and their waiting time, stratified by patient sex, age, emergency code, and major acute symptom at triage;
- number of those being treated and the average treatment time, stratified by patient sex, age, emergency code, and major acute symptom at triage;
- arrival time of ambulances, and the time to free them for the next emergency.

Data flow (Figure 4): The participating hospitals will prospectively collect the data, pre-process them (see below), and centralize them to the **organizational-eCREAM databases** (IRFMN).

Data classification: Aggregated (patients and hospital) data. Further information on the ED and hospital characteristics, such as the presence of specialized emergency rooms (e.g., obstetric, dermatologic, ophthalmic) or the level attributed to the hospital in the local trauma system, will be collected at the start of the project and updated twice a year.

Pre-processing of data: Data will be aggregated before the transfer from the hospital (data owner/controller) to IRFMN (data processor).

Legal basis for collecting and processing data: The approach described above makes the data fully anonymized; consequently, their processing falls outside the GDPR. Accordingly, the request for explicit consent to re-use this data should not be applicable.

The Case study 2 protocol will be submitted for approval to competent Ethical Committees and other decision bodies according to national laws.

Figure 4

Appendix 3. OPERATIONAL AND LEGAL QUESTIONNAIRE

Necessary to set up the legal framework for data use, reuse and sharing in the context of ecream project, following the kick-off meeting in bologna, nov 2022

Version 1 Final, ECRIN & IRFMN, 10/02/2023

Name, Function and contact details of the expert:

Country and organization:

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I. INTRODUCTION

BACKGROUND

The eCREAM project N°101057726 (Enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine) is a five year Horizon Europe project led by the Mario Negri Institute for Pharmacological Research (IRFMN, Italy). The eCREAM consortium includes 11 partners from 8 European countries: France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland, and the UK.

The main aim of the project is to enable clinical and quality of care assessment research using data extracted directly from electronic health records (EHR) of emergency departments (ED).

To reach this goal eCREAM has three main objectives:

To develop new technical solutions to extract reliable clinical information from structured and unstructured data contained in different electronic patient files;

To pilot the exploitation of the established databases in two relevant use cases: i) assessment of ed propensity to hospitalise a patient, and ii) development of a dashboard to be used by citizens and policymakers to improve the quality of care in ed

To fairify (i.e., making data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable) the established databases for clinicians, researchers, health policymakers and citizens while respecting the european and national legislations.

To achieve the project objectives, eCREAM will create three different databases of clinical data gathered from EDs located in six European countries: Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, UK.

PURPOSE OF THIS DOCUMENT

The project tasks involve data processing activities that require the use of patients related data extracted from the electronic health records (EHR) of emergency departments (ED).

In order to get some clarity on the legal and regulatory requirements which are applicable in relation to these activities as well as the conditions under which the participating hospitals can provide patient-related data in the context of eCREAM project, ECRIN as a leader of WP5 together with the coordinator team, have developed a specific questionnaire which addresses the operational and legal questions in relation to the data processing activities.

Ultimately, the answers provided through this questionnaire will be used as the basis (a) to develop a data management plan (Deliverable D.5.1.) as well as (b) to support the concerned parties in taking the necessary steps to fulfil the legal and regulatory requirements under the EU General Data Protection Regulation (the GDPR) and the relevant national laws and regulations as applicable. However, the ultimate responsibility for ensuring compliance with the applicable laws and regulations remains with the data providers and the data recipients as set out in the Consortium Agreement and the description of work.

CONTENT AND STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The questionnaire has been divided into 4 sections based on the project tasks involving data processing activities:

- **Development of NLP system**
- **CASE STUDY 1: measuring the propensity of eds to hospitalize patients**
- **CASE STUDY 2: development of a multipurpose dashboard for citizens and policymakers**
- **Integration of the databases and services to the medical informatics platform (MIP)**

Each section has been divided into two sub-sections: Operational (A) and Legal (B). Our assumption is that having a clear idea of the operational aspects and the associated data processing activities will help us determine the applicable legal framework.

The Operational section aims at describing the main project tasks, providing information on the types of data processing activities in these tasks, listing the main categories of personal data required to perform the tasks, clarifying the role and responsibilities of the parties involved in the data processing activities, etc. The information under this section will be collected from the Beneficiaries in charge of these activities and/or external service providers as applicable.

The Legal section aims at collecting information regarding the legal and regulatory framework based on the description of the data processing activities identified under the Operational section. The information under this section will be collected from the Data protection officers or/and the Legal departments of the hospitals providing data for the purpose of the project (the Data providers).

INSTRUCTIONS

The operational questions have been already addressed by the concerned Beneficiaries and their answers are being provided below under the sub-sections A. Operational questions.

As a member of the Legal expert group representing the hospitals providing patient-related data, you are expected to answer the questions listed under the sub-sections **B. Questions to be addressed by the DPO or/and Legal department of the organisation that will provide data for the development of the NLP system.**

Please carefully read the information provided under the sub-section **A. Operational questions** in order to become familiar with the project tasks and the associated data processing activities. Should you have additional questions in relation to the operational aspects, do not hesitate to discuss them with your colleagues involved in the project activities on behalf of your organisation.

After going through the description of data processing activities, please answer the questions under the sub-sections B. as well as the Final questions under the Section VI (pages 5,8,9,11). Do not hesitate to refer the questions to the relevant department within your organisation (legal, Data privacy/DPO, other) if necessary.

II. Development of the NLP system

A. Operational questions

- 1. As per the Description of Work, the personal data contained in the free texts will be anonymised prior to its transfer to FBK central server?**

Yes, free texts included in the clinical notes will be anonymised at the participating centre level and transferred to FBK central server.

- 2. Purpose of the anonymization: For what purpose do you need to anonymise the data (research activities, quality improvement studies, other)?**

Anonymised clinical notes will be used for research activities, specifically to instruct the artificial intelligence algorithm able to develop a system for natural language processing.

- 3. Please describe the data anonymisation techniques, methods and procedures that you are planning to use.**

Data will be anonymised at the participating centre level through an ad hoc software installed by [NAME of COMPANY(IES)] [Agreement under negotiation. The name of the company will be provided once the agreement has been established]. The software automatically analyses documents and datasets to identify, classify, and mask text portion containing personal identifiers and personally identifiable information according to the GDPR. The technical specifications on anonymisation techniques, methods and procedures will be provided to the hospital data protection officer and duly included in the study protocol.

- 4. Who will perform the anonymisation (hospital staff, external service provider, a Beneficiary to eCREAM GA, other, etc)?**

Data will be anonymised at the participating centre level by the hospital staff supported by [NAME of COMPANY(IES)].

- 5. Categories of personal data that will be subject to anonymisation (health data collected in the context of emergency department, data and charts on hospital admissions, images, biomedical samples, etc.), source and location of the data (e.g. hospital medical records (paper, electronic dossier, etc), clinical trial CRF, etc.)**

Free text will be extracted from the clinical notes included in the emergency department electronic medical records already collected by the hospital. Data will be collected retrospectively.

- 6. Do you intend to further use the data after the end of the project, or the data use will be limited to eCREAM activities? In case of further use, please indicate the purpose.**

Data collected and processed for the development of the natural language processing system will be stored at the FBK servers (Trento, Italy). Data will be anonymised, thus they are no longer subject to the GDPR. The algorithm developed through the anonymised clinical notes will be made available open source. Possible further use of the data after the end of the project will be limited to research activities.

7. Will the (anonymised!) data be transferred to a data repository outside the hospital? To another country? If yes, to EU/EEA country or outside the EU/EEA area?

The anonymized data will be transferred to a data repository outside the hospital hosted by FBK servers (Trento, Italy).

B. Questions to be addressed by the DPO or/and Legal department of the organisation that will provide data for the development of the NLP system

- 1. Does the process of anonymisation of patient data already collected in the hospital setting require specific permissions and authorisations under your national legal framework (authorisation by the data competent authorities/ethics committee, patients consent or another legal basis, etc)? Please describe the legal and regulatory requirements as well as the hospital procedures and policies necessary for processing the categories of data listed above to be used in the context of eCREAM project.**
- 2. In case of transfer of anonymised data to FBK, is such transfer allowed under your national legislation? If yes, under which conditions?**

III. CASE STUDY 1: Measuring the propensity of EDs to hospitalize patients

A. Operational questions

1. Please shortly describe the activity to be performed under the Case Study 1

ED performance is characterised by a series of decision-making steps, ranging from rapidly defining the priority with which patients will undergo a medical examination (triage), to establishing whether they need hospitalisation. IT-solutions developed by eCREAM will be tested in this latter scenario, one of the most critical in emergency medicine, due to the possible adverse consequences in both management (related to inappropriate hospitalisations) and clinical terms (related to inappropriate discharge). The decision to admit or discharge a patient from the ED is influenced, among other things, by patient-specific factors (e.g., medical condition), physician-specific factors (e.g., self-defined risk thresholds), hospital-specific factors (e.g., availability of medical resources), and societal-specific factors (e.g., presence of healthcare services).

eCREAM will build adjusted indicator(s) for measuring the propensity of EDs to hospitalize patients, focusing on people with loss of consciousness or dyspnoea at ED arrival.

2. Could you, please, indicate how Case Study 1 can be qualified?

Patients included in Case study 1 will be treated according to the ED routine clinical practice, and there will not be any additional data collection. Therefore, from a methodological point of view, the study design is purely observational.

The indicators developed will provide every ED with a thorough representation of its propensity to hospitalise patients, compared to the average behaviour, overall, over time, and according to the patient's probability of being hospitalised. Considering that the hospitalisation rate is one of the most commonly used indicators of the quality of care for Emergency Departments, this project will facilitate a revision of the clinical practice of the participating EDs to improve healthcare quality and outcomes. Case study 1 will, in other words, produce an unprecedented benchmarking model for quality-of-care assessment, allowing the monitoring of the propensity to admit patients of each ED, the comparison among different centres, and the planning of correcting measures.

Interestingly, the participation of several EDs from different countries, and the possibility of pooling their data for analysis, will allow for studying the determinants of the disposition decision in terms of patients' clinical characteristics, organizational models, and their interaction. Knowledge of these determinants will be essential not only for improving the quality of individual departments that participate in the project but also, and even more importantly, for directing policies to improve emergency medicine at large.

Ultimately, these activities represent an institutional duty of national health systems and are conducted in the public interest to improve the quality of emergency medicine.

3. Which categories of personal data will be used? Source? Location?

A specific set of clinical and organizational information (predictors) will be collected to feed the mathematical prediction model to estimate the propensity of each ED to hospitalize patients.

Clinical data will be collected at the patient level through the IT systems already in place at each ED. These data will include personal data concerning health, such as:

- characteristics of the patients, primarily age, sex, race/ethnicity, mode of arrival to the ED and arrival day/time;
- signs, symptoms and the attributed priority code;
- results of diagnostic procedures.

The full list of variables to be collected on patients with loss of consciousness or dyspnoea at ED arrival will be included in the study protocol.

Organizational data will be collected at the ED level through structured questionnaires to the ED staff/head. These data will not include personal data.

4. Will the data be anonymized or pseudonymised?

The participating EDs will prospectively collect the patient-level data through their IT-system. These data will be transferred in a pseudonymised format to the clinical-eCREAM database.

5. Does this activity involve the transfer of data to another site, EU/EEA country? Non eu/EEA country?

The **clinical-eCREAM database** will be hosted by the Mario Negri Institute (IRFMN) in Italy. Thus, pseudonymised data will be transferred from Greece, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, UK to Italy.

The data included in the clinical-eCREAM database will not be transferred outside the eCREAM Consortium, but they will be made accessible beyond eCREAM through the Medical Information Platform (MIP). MIP is an online collaborative tool managed by Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois (CHUV) in Switzerland that federates patient data located in different hospitals. Please, see the last part of this document for further information on how MIP works.

B. Questions to be addressed by the DPO and/or the Legal department of the organisation that will provide data for Case Study 1

1. On which legal basis your organisation can share patient-related personal data for the purposes stated under the USE CASE 1 above (public interest, legitimate interest, consent?)

Assumption based on the feasibility assessment performed by the coordinator of the project:

Considering the objectives of the data processing activities performed within Case study 1, the public interest of the expected outcome (to improve routine clinical practice in emergency departments by measuring the propensity of EDs to hospitalize patients) and given the context of the collection of personal data (patients admitted to the emergency departments who may not be in a capacity to provide consent), it might not always be feasible to acquire patients consent during the Emergency Department stay or to reach out to the patients who have left the emergency departments. As the GDPR allows for several legal bases for the processing of data for scientific research, we strongly recommend that an alternative lawful solution (legal basis) to consent would be to consider

2. What are the legal and regulatory requirements for the performance of such study under your national framework and for the processing of personal data (permissions, regulatory authorisations, patients' consent for research and patients' consent for the processing of personal data, etc.)?

3. Are there any other considerations or questions to be addressed in order to perform Case Study 1?

IV. CASE STUDY 2: Development of a multipurpose dashboard for citizens and policymakers

A. Operational questions

1. Please shortly describe the activity to be performed under Case study 2.

The aim of Case study 2 is to develop a multipurpose dashboard to inform end-users about predefined characteristics of the EDs in real time. We will set up the dashboard for two end-user categories: citizens and health policymakers. eCREAM will develop an App to be used by **citizens** to check the crowding level at each ED, the number of patients waiting by emergency code, and the average waiting time for the visit by emergency code. **Health policymakers** (including the head of the ED) will have access to data to monitor specific organizational (e.g., boarding time) and epidemiological (e.g., the emergence of infectious disease) phenomena.

2. Could you, please, indicate how Case Study 2 can be qualified?

As with Case study 1, patients will be treated according to the ED routine clinical practice, and there will not be any additional data collection. Thus, from a methodological point of view, the study design is observational.

3. Which categories of personal data will be used? Source? Location?

To create a real-time dashboard, the following aggregate data will be extracted from each ED every 5 minutes:

- number of patients awaiting a visit and their waiting time, stratified by patient sex, age, emergency code, and major acute symptom at triage;
- number of those being treated and the average treatment time, stratified by patient sex, age, emergency code, and major acute symptom at triage;
- arrival time of ambulances, and the time to free them for the next emergency.

Further information on the ED and hospital characteristics, such as the presence of specialized emergency rooms (e.g., obstetric, dermatologic, ophthalmic) or the level attributed to the hospital in the local trauma system, will be collected at the start of the project and updated twice a year.

4. The data will be anonymized or pseudonymised?

Aggregated (patients and hospital) data can be considered anonymised.

5. Does this activity involve the transfer of data to another site, EU/EEA country? Non eu/EEA country?

The **organizational-eCREAM** database will be hosted by the Mario Negri Institute (IRFMN) in Italy. Thus, anonymous aggregate data will be transferred from the hospitals in Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, UK to IRFMN in Italy. Aggregate data will be automatically extracted through a software (details will be included in the study protocol) and made available through an App after further processing by to IRFMN. The data presented to the end-user will be aggregate, will not contain any personal data and they cannot be used to re-identify patients admitted to any of the EDs. The data included in the organizational-eCREAM database will not be transferred outside the eCREAM consortium, but they will be made accessible beyond eCREAM through the Medical Information Platform (MIP). MIP is an online collaborative tool managed by Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois (CHUV) in Switzerland that federates patient data located in different hospitals. Please, see the last part of this document for further information on how MIP works.

B. Questions to be addressed by the DPO and/or the Legal department of the organisation that will provide data for Case Study 2

1. What are the legal and regulatory requirements for the performance of such study under your national framework and for the processing of personal data (permissions, regulatory authorisations, patients' consent for research and patients' consent for the processing of personal data, etc)?

2. Are there any other considerations, questions to be addressed in order to perform the Case study 2.

V. Integration of the databases and services to the Medical Informatics Platform (MIP)

A. Operational questions

1. Describe the MIP in a few words (functionalities and purpose, location, owner, categories of personal data will be transferred to the MIP):

- Privacy-preserving, federated data processing and analysis system.
- Leverage and re-use of de-centralised patient data and research cohort datasets.
- Exploration of anonymised, harmonised medical data.
- Integrated statistical methods and predictive machine learning algorithms for data exploration and modelling.
- Data do not need to leave their original site of storage
- Exploiting the value of clinical information that cannot be centralized
- Code Visits Data -minimally invasive in IT, ethics and legal context through virtual appliance technology
- Easily accessible UI tailored for clinicians, no expert programming knowledge needed

Location: the central MIP research infrastructure is part of the HBP, EBRAINS RI, being hosted on the CSCS, Swiss National Supercomputing Centre in Lugano, CH; the remote node installations of MIP federated nodes are in the specific institutions willing to join the federation (various countries)

Product Owner: CHUV, Lausanne Switzerland, Philippe Ryvlin, co-development with 2 other teams in HBP from Greece (Athena RC, AUEB)

2. How does aggregation of data work?

There will be 15 federated Algorithms available for analysis.

Data privacy preservation: end-users query datasets on remote nodes and retrieve aggregated findings, no investigation of datasets at the individual level. Datasets cannot be directly accessed, copied, uploaded or downloaded.

The Central MIP engine hosted by the EBRAINS RI, enables federated web-based queries which will execute the same algorithm in each node in a coordinated way, to provide aggregated findings to the accredited users (results calculated on each node, aggregated at the central MIP node before the user will receive the result of the query)

Implemented privacy threshold: 10 records at least, otherwise no result will be computed in order to avoid singling out single records)

3. Do you intend to further use the data after the end of the project, or the data use will be limited to eCREAM activities? In case of further use, please indicate the purpose.

The MIP only provides the platform, data retention will be defined by eCREAM. Public Datasets on the MIP Public are supposed to be available also after the end of eCREAM.

B. Questions to be addressed by the DPO and/or the Legal department of the organisation that will provide data for data sharing via MIP

- 1. What are the legal and regulatory requirements for the Integration of the databases and services to the Medical Informatics Platform (MIP) under your national framework (permissions, regulatory authorisations, patients' consent for research and patients' consent for the processing of personal data, etc)?**
- 2. Are there any other considerations, questions to be addressed in order to perform this activity?**

VI. Final questions:

- 1. Are there any other additional data processing activities that might be involved in the eCREAM project and that have not been considered in this questionnaire?**
- 2. Which department(s)/whom should be contacted, at your organisation, to take care of the regulatory and legal requirements with regards to the processing of personal data within the eCream?**